

SECTION 2: MULTI-TOPICS 2022

COMMUNICATION PLAN

PAS-AGRO-PAS

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive,
Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional
Agro-pastoralism

PAS - AGRO - PAS

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PREAMBLE

This Communication Plan (CP) delineates the strategies and methodologies that the PAS-AGRO-PAS project participants will utilize throughout the project's execution to efficiently communicate the project's concept, achievements, and key messages to the intended audiences through appropriate communication channels. The CP was discussed on the online meeting on 10th October 2023. In essence, this comprehensive CP adheres closely to the fundamental principles outlined in the original project proposal, with minimal deviation.

The project participants:

1 : POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE OF BRAGANÇA, PORTUGAL

Represented by: Vasco Cadavez

Hereafter referred to as **IPB**

2 : ERATOSTHENES CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE, CYPRUS UNIV OF TECHNOLOGY, CYPRUS

Represented by: Ouranios Tzamaloukas

Hereafter referred to as **ECoE**

3 : ANIMAL PRODUCTION RESEARCH INSTITUTE, EGYPT

Represented by: Adel Abounaga

Hereafter referred to as **APRI**

4 : SYSTÈMES D'ELEVAGE MÉDITERRANÉENS ET TROPICAUX, FRANCE

Represented by: Amandine Lurette

Hereafter referred to as **SELMET**

5 : MODÉLISATION SYSTÉMIQUE APPLIQUÉE AUX RUMINANTS, FRANCE

Represented by: Laurence Puillet

Hereafter referred to as **MoSAR**

6 : UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI SASSARI, ITALY

Represented by: Antonello Cannas

Hereafter referred to as **UNISS**

7 : INSTITUT AGRONOMIQUE ET VÉTÉRINAIRE HASSAN II, MOROCCO

Represented by: Abdelilah Araba

Hereafter referred to as **IAV**

8 : UNIVERSITY IBN ZOHR, MOROCCO

Represented by: Fouad Achemchem

Hereafter referred to as **UIZ**

9 : CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DE LA CARNE, SPAIN

Represented by: José Manuel Lorenzo

Hereafter referred to as **CTC**

10 : INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO AGRARIO DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN, SPAIN

Represented by: Raúl Bodas

Hereafter referred to as **ITACyL**

11 : Arid Zone Research Institute (Institut des Régions Arides), Tunisia

Represented by: Halima Elhatmi

Hereafter referred to as **IRA**

now wish to set up the mechanisms and channels for the communication of the concept and outcomes of the PAS-AGRO-PAS Project, and their respective commitments and timelines resulting thereof.

1. THE PROJECT MANAGEMENT TEAM (PMT)

The Project Management Team (PMT) consists of key members who play crucial roles in ensuring the effective management and coordination of the project. The PMT is composed of the following members:

Coordinator: Vasco Cadavez (IPB)

Project Vice-Coordinator: Ursula Gonzales-Barron (IPB)

IPR & Exploitation Manager: José Santos (IPB)

Communication and Dissemination Managers: Fouad Achemchem (UIZ) and Ouranios Tzamaloukas (ECoE)

The primary responsibilities of the PMT include:

- a) Assisting the Coordinator in the day-to-day management of the project, including handling legal and administrative matters;
- b) Monitoring, supporting, and facilitating the communication of the project's progress;
- c) Establishing procedures for internal consortium communication and the collection of reports and deliverables;
- d) Assisting the Coordinator in financial management and gathering financial statements from the project partners;
- e) Supporting the organization, preparation, and follow-up of periodic meetings;
- f) Providing guidance and support to the partners regarding procedures mandated by H2020 regulations.

Figure 1. The PAS-AGRO-PAS's Project Management Team

The Communication and Dissemination Managers will play a vital role in facilitating both internal and external communication activities, working closely with the Executive Board and the Coordinator. Their specific responsibilities encompass:

- a) Identifying novel channels for disseminating the PAS-AGRO-PAS concept and monitoring their implementation;
- b) Tracking the project's outcomes to propose effective strategies for dissemination at forthcoming events;
- c) Providing support for communication, dissemination, and networking endeavors in alignment with the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results;
- d) Collaborating with Principal Investigators (PIs) to oversee and offer assistance in organizing local workshops;
- e) Coordinating the creation of promotional materials, the project's newsletter, and ensuring the continuous updating of the project website and social media platforms;
- f) Vigilantly overseeing the ongoing update of the "PAS-AGRO-PAS Methods Pack" on the consortium's website portal by the partners.

2. KEY MESSAGES

The primary messages to be disseminated from the PAS-AGRO-PAS project encompass three core aspects: the concept, the scientific outputs and the significance.

2.1 The concept

The PAS-AGRO-PAS concept will be actively communicated and promoted right from the inception of the project, employing a diverse range of communication channels. These channels will include the project's website, meetings, printed materials, and social media platforms. Each partner within the PAS-AGRO-PAS consortium will undertake the dissemination of the project's concept at a minimum of one international or local event during the first year. This dissemination can take the form of informative leaflets or presentations at international or local events.

As the project progresses into its second and third years, the concept, along with scientific outputs, will be shared during local workshops scheduled to take place in every Mediterranean country. Furthermore, a comprehensive dissemination effort will culminate in the Final Seminar held at the conclusion of the project, ensuring that the concept and research findings reach a wide and engaged audience.

2.2 The scientific outputs

The scientific outputs, often referred to as results, will be communicated in the second and third years of the project. These communications will be facilitated through various channels, including the project's website, the Zenodo community, the GitHub, the participation in international or national scientific conferences, engagement in local industrial workshops, and through presentation in the Final Seminar, which is slated to occur at the project's conclusion.

2.3 The significance

The significance of the project encompasses its implications, relevance, applications, and the path forward that can be derived from the scientific outputs. The channels chosen for communicating the project's significance remain consistent with those for the scientific outputs. However, the audience targeted for this communication will primarily include Agro-pastoralists, associations, public bodies, and policy and decision-makers.

3. TARGET AUDIENCES

3.1 Research institutions

Communication channels with research institutions will be diverse and encompass various avenues, including:

Education: Sharing knowledge and insights through educational initiatives, such as workshops, seminars, and training sessions, to foster collaboration and learning among researchers.

Publications: Disseminating research findings and outcomes through academic and scientific publications, ensuring that the broader research community can access and build upon the work.

New Research Projects: Collaborating on and initiating new research projects that stem from the knowledge and discoveries generated within the PAS-AGRO-PAS project.

Patents: Protecting and potentially commercializing innovative discoveries through patents, encouraging further research and applications.

Joint Ventures: Engaging in collaborative ventures with other research institutions, fostering cross-institutional cooperation and sharing of resources and expertise.

Spin-offs: Establishing spin-off companies or initiatives that can directly apply research findings in practical settings, driving innovation and economic growth.

PAS-AGRO-PAS's researchers will actively verify and reuse data and models generated within the project, while also facilitating data reuse for other researchers through open-access publications. These efforts contribute to the broader scientific community's ability to leverage the project's findings for additional research and applications.

3.2 Agro-pastoralists and Agro-foods producers

Agro-pastoralists who are participating in the project will directly reap the benefits of the project's outcomes. These outcomes will empower them to enhance the layout of their facilities, employ effective strategies, and implement in-process quality monitoring tools to ensure the production of high-quality and safety-assured agro-pastoral products. The channels of communication with agro-pastoralists encompass the annual workshops scheduled for the second and third years, the participation of the researchers involved of the project in conferences and seminars promoting the use of forages/agropastoralism, the protected area of the project's website, the divulgation via popular agri-food journals and the final PAS-AGRO-PAS Seminar.

The developed decision-support tools will be provided to the participating agro-pastoralists and agro-food producers. Furthermore, other agro-pastoralists engaged in any of the livestock or breeds investigated in the PAS-AGRO-PAS project may also access

and utilize these tools, subject to conditions outlined in the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results.

3.3 Start-ups and investors

Industrial and/or financial investors can find business opportunities from the outputs that the PAS-AGRO-PAS project will generate. Business opportunities are related to the use of byproducts, or the extraction of bioactive compounds for use in meat and dairy products (example, a local start-up) and the provision of solutions for new food products based on agropastoralism bio-preservation and process risk models (example, a service provider). The channels of communication and interaction are the website, project initiatives, information material, social media, stakeholder platforms, etc.

3.4 Public bodies and policy makers

Public bodies are instrumental in enabling a high coverage on quality harmonisation of the regional products manufactured by the stakeholders involved in agropastoralism, by means of further educational and divulgation events. Finally, policy and decision-makers will be targeted by providing scientific-based endorsement for the origin or quality certification of the artisanal or agropastoral food products. The channels of communication and interaction are the website, project initiatives, divulgation material and invitation to some of the industrial workshops and the final PAS-AGRO-PAS Seminar. Information on the progress of the project will be disseminated to the general public through the social networks of the participating institutions.

4. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The external channels of communication that will be implemented in the PAS-AGRO-PAS project are explained in detail as follows.

4.1 The PAS-AGRO-PAS's website

Utilizing the corporate identity and graphic templates of the PAS-AGRO-PAS project, we will create and maintain the project's website for a minimum of three years beyond the project's duration. The website will feature three distinct portals:

- a) **Public Portal:** This will serve as the central dissemination channel for sharing information related to the project's concept, results, and outreach activities. It will also provide downloadable resources such as leaflets and newsletters. External users will have the option to register for regular updates.
- b) **Intra-consortium Portal:** This portal, protected by a password, will facilitate information sharing among the multidisciplinary consortium members. It will include collaborative workspaces, interactive communication tools, and a platform for developing and updating the "Methods Pack".
- c) **Web Interface for the PAS-AGRO-PAS Safety Decision-Support Tool:** This interface will be implemented towards the end of the project and will be accessible to participating agro-pastoralists and food producers.

The website's content will primarily be prepared in English, but materials produced locally or news on partners' participation in local events can be uploaded in other Mediterranean languages such as Arabic, French, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, or Spanish. However, these materials will include a concise English synopsis for cataloguing purposes.

The Project Coordinator will be responsible for populating, updating, and maintaining the website, incorporating materials provided and approved by the partners. The website will be hosted on the server of the IPB partner.

The public portal of the website will include:

- The PAS-AGRO-PAS concept
- Brief biographies of the researchers involved
- General flow diagrams of the meat and dairy products under study
- Results and links to scientific articles published by the consortium
- PDF versions of articles whenever feasible
- Updates on training and dissemination events organized by the consortium
- Reports on scientific conferences attended by consortium members
- Information on collaborations with other networks and project initiatives, when non-confidential.

4.2 Scientific divulgation

As the project progresses, two forms of scientific dissemination will be implemented: (i) scientific articles; and (ii) presentations at scientific conferences and technical meetings (Table 1).

a) Scientific Publications: Scientific publications will take the form of reviews, and primary research articles. For these publications, the participating partner Principal Investigators (PIs), after agreeing upon and revising the manuscript contents, will decide whether to publish in an open-access journal.

Seven papers will be authored by CTC and other partners covering the following themes:

- "Effect of the feeding type on carcass and meat quality of Galician sheep" This article is expected to be published by October 2025.
- "Influence of the finishing diet on carcass characteristics and meat quality of Galician goat". This article is expected to be published by November 2025.
- "Shelf-life improvement of sheep burgers enriched with natural antioxidants". This article is expected to be published by January 2026.
- "Employ of microencapsulated healthy oils to enhance the nutritional profile of lamb pâtés". This article is expected to be published by March 2026.
- "Effect of rearing system on meat quality of Castellana and Churra lambs". This article is expected to be published by March 2026.
- "Effect of different crop allies and management strategies on soil health and crop performance". Expected to be published by March 2026.
- "Development of functional dry-fermented lamb sausages". This article is expected to be published by May 2026.

Three articles or announcements on scientific conferences will be produced regarding the effect of a management practice that is very common in grazing animals (partial suckling of lambs/kids) on the quality and the quantity of milk

produced as well as on the metabolism of mammary tissue. This scientific communication would take place between November 2024 and December 2026.

Three articles or announcements on scientific conferences will be produced on the use of high proportion of forages or byproducts in the animal diets as used in agropastoralism compared to the low forage participation in the diets as applied in common dairy production in Cyprus. These announcements would take place between June 2025 and December 2026.

One paper will be authored by MoSAR, covering the theme of methane emissions in dairy goats from two genetic lines, divergent for longevity. The article is expected by the end of 2026 and results will also be presented at an international conference.

Three papers will be authored by Selmet and MoSAR (co-supervision of PhD project), covering the following topics:

- Sensitivity analysis and statistical exploration of the range of viability for a simulation model combining demographic processes and management rules. This article is expected by the end of 2025.
- Sustainability of small ruminant pastoral systems implementing adaptation strategies. This article is expected by the end of 2026.
- Cross-sectional analysis of the constraints/opportunities provided by the sectors to design more sustainable pastoral livestock system: case study of dairy goats and suckler sheep in southern France. This article is expected by the end of 2026.

These articles will also be presented as communications in a French conference (end 2026) and at EAAP (2025 and 2026).

b) Scientific Conferences and Technical Meetings: Project partners will disseminate the project's results at both international and national scientific congresses, as well as during local educational and technical meetings.

Table 1. Partners involved and timeline for the scientific divulgation activities

Kind of scientific divulgation	Partner	Timeline and frequency
Scientific publications Five papers Various Primary research articles	CTC, IPB Other partners	October 2025 – May 2026 Until May 2026
Scientific conferences First year Second year Third year	UIZ All All	Once, November 2023 At least once per partner At least once per partner
Technical meetings First year Second year Third year	IPB All All	Once, July 2023 At least once per partner At least once per partner

4.3 Production of divulgation materials

Throughout the project's duration, various types of dissemination materials will be

generated to ensure the visibility of the consortium and the promotion and uptake of the project's outcomes (Table 2). These materials will be available in electronic formats, tailored to specific target audiences.

- a) **Printed Leaflets:** These leaflets will outline key elements of the project and will be distributed during relevant local and/or international conferences and through partner networks. They will be produced in either English or a Mediterranean language, depending on the target audience and the location of the event.
- b) **Press and Media Materials:** Texts for press and media will be composed in English and shared with European media outlets. These materials will also be translated, as needed, for distribution to national and local journals by each partner.
- c) **Project E-Newsletters:** Regular e-newsletters will be created to provide updates on the project's progress, feature interviews with artisanal producers, announce upcoming meetings and workshops, and share other relevant news. These newsletters will be sent annually to subscribers of the PAS-AGRO-PAS website.

Table 2. Partners involved and timeline for the production of divulgation materials

Kind of divulgation materials	Partner	Timeline and frequency
Printed leaflets	All	At least once a year per partner
Press and media texts European press	Led by UIZ	Once, April 2024
Local interview with sheep association leaders Post on the social media of ECoE lab regarding the benefits of agropastoralism	ECoE	Once per partner, May to Dec 2024
E-newsletters		
First year	Led by IPB, populated by all	Once, May 2024
Second year	Led by ECoE, populated by all	Once, May 2025
Third year	Led by UIZ, populated by all	Once, May 2026

4.4 Social media

Account of social media will be created for the PAS-AGRO-PAS project in LinkedIn and Facebook. This account will be managed by UIZ, and it will be consistently updated with information contributed by all project partners.

4.5 Local workshops with agro-pastoralists

Local workshops or seminars will be arranged by each partner, primarily gathering agro-pastoralists and agro-food producers involved in agropastoralism. However, other stakeholders such as the research community, policymakers, and interest groups may also

be invited. During these workshops, the project's outcomes will be shared with regional industries, and recommendations will be offered based on project progress. Each partner will host one workshop by the end of the second year and another before the project's conclusion. These workshops will include a dedicated seminar session aimed at engaging key stakeholders who are not project partners, such as agro-pastoralist and agro-food producer associations, national regulators, policymakers and other researchers. The goal is to gather opinions and inputs for planned activities and, most importantly, to enhance opportunities for result exploitation.

4.6 The PAS-AGRO-PAS Seminar

The Consortium will organize the PAS-AGRO-PAS Seminar as a final public dissemination event, targeting various agro-pastoralists and organizations of agro-pastoralists, European and national regulators/policymakers, researchers, public bodies, investors, and consumers. This event will conclude the project's outcomes and will include the following components:

- ◆ Presenting the newly developed PAS-AGRO-PAS decision-support tool.
- ◆ Disseminating informational materials.
- ◆ Providing recommendations for agro-pastoralists and regional industries involved in this activity, as well as policymakers.
- ◆ Offering suggestions for future research and cooperation agendas.

Special sessions and exhibition booths will be arranged to:

- (i) Explain the usage of the decision-support tool to interested parties, including other Mediterranean agro-food industries, academic researchers, and European/national policymakers interested in the improvements in quality and process standardization of agro-food issued from agropastoralism.
- (ii) Share details about the exploitation of project results and investment opportunities.
- (iii) Gather expressions of interest for future collaborations and spin-offs that will expand and sustain the PAS-AGRO-PAS decision-support tool.
- (vi) Contribute to the preservation of the livelihoods of disadvantaged agro-pastoral households affected by the pastoral crisis.
- (v) Promote the appreciation of Mediterranean agro-pastoral foods by highlighting their exceptional quality, rich tradition, and significant contributions to regional development through live demonstrations of preparation and cooking techniques at exhibition booths.

5. RECORDS OF THE COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The ongoing communication activities, as planned and outlined in the present CP, will be recorded by each of the project participant, by filling out Table 3. The Communication and Dissemination Managers will request from each partner an update to this Table every three months.

Table 3. Record sheet of the communication activities (Completed until 31st November 2024)

Type	Date, Estimated EUR Amount, Audience, Language, etc
Organisation of a Conference	
Organisation of Workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valorization strategies of sheep and goat meat: healthy meat products” at CTC Institute (Ourense, Spain), March 2026, Spanish language. • Workshop with the name “The feed sufficiency issue in Cyprus, covering the animal needs from alternative forages, agropastoralism and by-products” June 2025, Greek Language.
Press release	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of forage/roughage in dairy production in Cyprus. Problems and possible Solutions. Greek Language, Local press, Cyprus, Nov 2025
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One publication on “Razas autóctonas” Journal authored by CTC, December 2025, Spanish language. • One publication on “Eurocarne” Journal authored by CTC, March 2026, Spanish language. • One publication on “Tierras Ovino” journal, authored by ITACyL. December 2025. Spanish language. • One publication on “Albéitar” journal, authored by ITACyL. October 2025. Spanish language.
Exhibition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Flyers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A flyer of the use of alternative forages and olive oil byproduct will be prepared for general use. Greek language; June 2026.
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term training will take place for new professionals to disseminate results and practices tested during the project (alternative forages, partial suckling of kids and lambs, the use of byproducts) Greek language, Between Sep 2025 and June 2026.
Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn, Facebook.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn and Facebook sites of the Animal and Dairy Science Department will host information on the project results and events promoting agropastoralism (on-going process Sep 2024 to Dec 2028) suggesting the use of byproducts and alternative forages.
<p>Participation to a Conference/Congress</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XLVIII Congreso Nacional y XXIV Internacional de la Sociedad Española de Ovinotecnia y Caprinotecnia” (SEOC 2025), place and date not defined yet, Spanish language; “XLV Congreso Nacional y XXV Internacional de la Sociedad Española de Ovinotecnia y Caprinotecnia” (SEOC 2026), place and date not defined yet, Spanish language. • 2nd Pancyriot Conference "Agricultural development: From Research to Practice" the title of presentation “The Making of Fragile Agro- ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism" Nov 2023, Nicosia, Cyprus. • 7th national conference “Dairy Agriculture and Livestock” organised by the stakeholders of dairy production in Cyprus. The title of the talk “Milk production, roughage sufficiency and climate change: How to solve the problem of unstable and insufficient production with research, education and policy choices” June 2024, Greek Language. • 76th Annual Meeting of the European Federation of Animal Science” (EAAP 2026), Hamburg (Germany), date not defined, English language, showing results on partial suckling on milk quantity, quality and mammary physiology. • 3rd Pancyriot Conference "Agricultural development: From Research to Practice" the title of presentation would be related to the alternative feeding practices in sheep and goat produciton " March 2025, Nicosia, Cyprus.
<p>Participation to a Workshop</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop organised by the sheep producers’ association “Poihmenas” the use of forage/roughage in dairy production. Greek language. July 2024. Limassol Cyprus. • 2nd Workshop organised by the sheep producers’ association “Poihmenas” with presentations regarding the use of forage/roughage and by-products in sheep and goat production. Greek language. July 2024. Limassol Cyprus. • 3rd Workshop organised by the sheep producers’ association “Poihmenas” with presentations regarding the use of forage/roughage and by-products in sheep and goat production. Greek language. July 2024. Limassol Cyprus.

Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	•
Web site	• Participation in the material uploaded in the project website.
Communication campaign (e.g., radio, tv, ...)	•
Video/film	• A video will be prepared regarding the experimentation and the techniques tested during the project. June 2026. Greek language and English subtitles.
Pitch event	•
Trade fair	•
Participation in activities organised jointly with other PRIMA/H2020 project(s)	•
